

IN-SITU STUDY OF THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF BIOINSPIRED ALUMINA-BASED COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT COMPLIANT POLYMER PHASES

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Background

- Dental crowns are prosthetics used to replace damaged or missing teeth
- All-ceramic crowns, usually made of alumina or zirconia, are popular choice due to almost natural aesthetics
- Dental ceramics are harder and stiffer than natural teeth and tend to have low fracture toughness
- Introduction of a polymer phase in combination with a bio-inspired microstructure can create materials that are softer, less stiff, with higher fracture toughness

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Methods

- Nacre-like alumina scaffolds were manufactured using a bidirectional freeze-casting technique
- 4 groups of 60% ceramic composites were prepared – PMMA, Epoxy, UDMA, and PU
- Cyclic and monotonic fracture toughness tests were performed using in situ SEM 3-point bending
- R-curve behaviour was determined according to the ASTM E1820 standard

Fig. 1 Diagram of the bidirectional freeze-casting process. Algharaibeh et al. J Eur Ceram Soc, 39:2-3 (2019): 514-21

Fig. 2 3-point bending fracture toughness tests were performed using a Deben Microtest stage inside a Tescan MIRA II.

Outcomes

- Fracture toughness testing showed that alumina-PMMA had the highest toughness whilst alumina-PU had the lowest
- PMMA > Epoxy > UDMA > PU
- K_{Jc} values measured using cyclic testing ranged from 6.11 ± 1.14 – 11.37 ± 2.4 $\text{MPa.m}^{0.5}$
- K_{Jc} values measured using monotonic testing ranged from 8.51 ± 0.23 – 12.12 ± 2.23 $\text{MPa.m}^{0.5}$

Fig. 3: Representative load-displacement curves of monotonic and cyclic testing of 60% alumina-PMMA nacre-like composites.

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Thank you for your attention!